

Synthesis and antibacterial studies of lanthanide(III) complexes with aminopromazine

B. Keshavan* and R. T. Radhika

Department of Studies in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Mysore-570 006, India

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New complexes of lanthanide(III) nitrates with aminopromazine, having the general formula $[\text{Ln}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$ (Ln = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu and AP = aminopromazine) have been synthesised. The complexes have been screened for antibacterial activities.

N-Alkylphenothiazines possess anticholinergic, antihistamine and antiamebic activities^{1,2}. Biologically active complexes of titanium(IV)³, zirconium(IV)⁴ and thorium(IV)⁵ with *N*-alkylphenothiazines have been reported. In view of the growing interest in lanthanides and their complexes, we report herein the synthesis of lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes with aminopromazine (10-[2,3-bis(dimethylamino)propyl]phenothiazine).

Aminopromazine Fumarate

Results and Discussion

The interaction of lanthanide(III) nitrates with aminopromazine fumarate in aqueous solutions yield lanthanide(III) nitrate-aminopromazine complexes. The fumarate ion goes into solution during the reaction and do not participate in coordination with lanthanide(III) nitrates.

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) suggest the stoichiometry $[\text{Ln}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$. The complexes are non-hygroscopic and stable at room temperature. They are soluble in DMF and DMSO, slightly soluble in acetonitrile and chloroform and insoluble in water and other common organic solvents. They do not possess sharp melting points. The molar conductances of the complexes ($85-95 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggest their 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour. The magnetic moment values in polycrystalline state determined at room temperature (Table 1) indicate that the La and Lu complexes are diamagnetic and the Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm and Yb complexes are paramagnetic. The

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic data of lanthanide(III)-aminopromazine complexes*

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
	Ln	NO_3^- (ionic)**	
$[\text{La}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.15 (14.17)	0.064 (0.063)	Dia
$[\text{Ce}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.19 (14.28)	0.063 (0.063)	2.61
$[\text{Pr}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.26 (14.35)	0.063 (0.063)	3.39
$[\text{Nd}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	14.55 (14.64)	0.062 (0.063)	3.67
$[\text{Sm}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	15.08 (15.17)	0.062 (0.063)	1.92
$[\text{Eu}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	15.22 (15.30)	0.062 (0.062)	3.74
$[\text{Gd}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	15.68 (15.75)	0.062 (0.062)	7.78
$[\text{Tb}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	15.81 (15.89)	0.062 (0.062)	9.97
$[\text{Dy}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.12 (16.19)	0.061 (0.062)	10.40
$[\text{Ho}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.33 (16.39)	0.061 (0.062)	10.34
$[\text{Er}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.52 (16.58)	0.061 (0.062)	9.29
$[\text{Tm}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	16.80 (16.72)	0.062 (0.061)	7.76
$[\text{Yb}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.04 (17.06)	0.061 (0.061)	4.86
$[\text{Lu}(\text{AP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$	17.12 (17.22)	0.061 (0.061)	Dia

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Sample taken for the determination of ionic nitrate = 1.0 g.

values found are close to the theoretical values calculated using the formula⁶, $\mu = g\sqrt{J(J+1)}$, suggesting the non-participation of *f*-electron in bonding and also show little deviations from Van Vleck values⁷, indicating minor par-

participation of the 4*f*-electrons in bonding.

Ir spectra : The ir band observed at 2865 cm⁻¹ of the aminopromazine fumarate may be due to the heterocyclic nitrogen atom attached to the bis(dimethylamino)propyl group. In the spectra of the complexes, this band shifted to 2850–2840 cm⁻¹ region, suggesting coordination of the heterocyclic nitrogen atom. A sharp band at 2785 cm⁻¹ of aminopromazine fumarate corresponds to the interaction of RNH⁺ with X⁻ (where R = propyl and X = fumarate)¹. In the spectra of the lanthanide(III) complexes this band shifted to 2960–2940 cm⁻¹, indicating participation of tertiary nitrogen atom of the side-chain on coordination. This shows that aminopromazine acts as a bidentate ligand. The sharp ligand band at 750 cm⁻¹ (CSC)⁸ remained unaffected in the spectra of the complexes supporting the non-coordination of heterocyclic sulphur atom.

The nitrate complexes exhibited four bands at 1465–1457, 1262–1253, 1055–1050 and 827–822 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the vibrational modes of coordination (C_{2v}) nitrate groups⁹. The magnitude of splitting of the bands at higher energies (about 200 cm⁻¹) suggests that the nitrate groups are attached to the metal atom in a bidentate fashion. The band observed at 1392–1384 cm⁻¹ is due to the ionic nitrate in the complexes. This indicates that all the lanthanide(III) complexes have both ionic and coordinated nitrate groups. The new bands observed at 455–450 cm⁻¹ due to (Ln–N)¹⁰ mode confirm the participation of the nitrogen atoms of aminopromazine on coordination.

¹H nmr spectra : The ¹H nmr spectrum of aminopromazine fumarate showed signals at δ 2.8–2.5 (d, N–CH₃), 3.55 (s, N–CH₂) and 6.82–7.13 (m, ArH). In the lanthanum and lutetium complexes the signals corresponding to –N–CH₃ protons shifted to lower frequency region (δ 2.37–3.65 and 2.39–2.68 respectively) and that corresponding to –N–CH₂ protons to lower frequency region (δ 3.65 and 3.78 respectively), indicating that the tertiary nitrogen atom of the side-chain and the heterocyclic nitrogen atom are coordinated to the metal ion. The signals for aromatic protons of benzene ring in the complexes were found at δ 6.85–7.26 and 6.87–7.31 respectively. The downfield shift in the absorption peaks of the complexes compared to the free ligand may be attributed to the corresponding effect of the nitrogen atoms, which results in deshielding of protons attached to it.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectrum of aminopromazine fumarate showed *n* → *π** and *π* → *π** transitions at 32362 and 37037 cm⁻¹ respectively. In the complexes they blue-shifted to 32786–32467 and 37453–37174 cm⁻¹ respectively. The spectral data of the Pr, Nd and Er complexes and their tentative assignments are given in Table 2, along with interelectronic repulsion parameter (*β*), percentage covalency (*δ*%), bonding parameter (*b*^{1/2}) and covalency angular overlap parameter (*η*) calculated¹¹. The values of *β* are less than unity, and *b*^{1/2} and *η* are positive, suggesting covalency in the metal-ligand bonding. The shapes of the hypersensitive transition closely resembles with that of the reported¹² eight-coordinated complexes. The elec-

Table 2. Electronic spectral* data (cm⁻¹) and related bonding parameters of lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes of aminopromazine

Ln(NO ₃) ₃	Complex	Assignment	<i>ε</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>b</i> ^{1/2}	<i>δ</i> %	<i>η</i>
Pr(NO ₃) ₃	[Pr(AP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃						
22222	22075	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	982.9	0.9934	0.0574	0.6643	0.0033
21276	21165	→ ³ P ₁	681.9	0.9948	0.0509	0.52227	0.0026
20408	20215	→ ³ P ₀	402.3	0.9905	0.0687	0.9547	0.0047
16949	16925	→ ¹ D ₂	330.6	0.9986	0.0264	0.1400	0.0007
Nd(NO ₃) ₃	[Nd(AP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃						
19607	19520	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{9/2}	1008.7	0.9955	0.0672	0.4456	0.0022
17241	17177	→ ⁴ G _{5/2} , ² G _{7/2}	1619.7	0.9963	0.0331	0.3713	0.0018
14705	14672	→ ⁴ F _{9/2}	421.3	0.9978	0.0308	0.2204	0.0010
13513	13487	→ ² S _{3/2} , ⁴ F _{7/2}	1443.6	0.9981	0.0290	0.1903	0.0009
12500	12420	→ ⁴ F _{5/2}	1420.2	0.9936	0.0565	0.6441	0.0032
Er(NO ₃) ₃	[Er(AP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃						
20408	20334	⁴ I _{15/2} → ² F _{7/2}	366.5	0.9964	0.0424	0.3613	0.0018
19230	19133	→ ² H _{11/2}	661.5	0.9950	0.0500	0.5025	0.0025
18867	18710	→ ⁴ S _{3/2}	562.2	0.9916	0.0645	0.8391	0.0041
15384	15264	→ ⁴ F _{9/2}	358.5	0.9922	0.0624	0.7861	0.0039

tronic spectral parameters also suggest weak covalent nature¹³ of the metal-ligand bonds.

Thermal studies : The thermal studies indicate that all the lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes are stable upto 230°, which shows that there are no coordinated water and solvent molecules. The complexes underwent two-stage decomposition, at 260–400° due to the organic moiety and at 420–760° due to nitrate followed by the formation of lanthanide(III) oxides. The residue remained constant at 780°. The DTA studies indicate that both the decomposition of organic moiety and the formation of lanthanide(III) oxides are exothermic processes.

Antibacterial activities : The results of antibacterial activities of the ligand and complexes show that aminopromazine fumarate solution does not show any antibacterial activity. The complexes are not active against *E. coli*, but the growth of *B. subtilis sp*, *S. aureus* and *S. sp* are inhibited by them (zone of inhibition 1.5, 2.0 and 1.5 mm at 1000 ppm respectively).

Experimental

The nitrates of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb and Dy (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and Ho, Er, Tm, Yb and Lu (Aldrich), and aminopromazine fumarate (Rhone Poulenc, France) were used. All other chemicals and solvents were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of the complexes : An aqueous solution of aminopromazine fumarate (6.0 mmol) was added to an aqueous solution of lanthanide(III) nitrates (2.5 mmol) with continuous stirring. The complexes formed were set aside for 1 h, filtered, washed with water followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂.

C, H and N were determined with a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyser. Metals¹⁴ (pH, 4.4–5.5) and ionic nitrate¹⁵ were estimated. Molar conductance was measured in 10⁻³ DMF solutions using digital an Elico conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 470 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Hitachi R-600 spectrometer with respect to TMS and electronic spectra (DMF) on a JASCO UVIDEDEC-610 spectrophotometer.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method at room temperature using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. Thermal analysis was carried out on a RIGAKU-TAS-100 instrument with a linear heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ in static air.

The antibacterial activities of the ligand and the complexes (concentrations 1000, 2000 and 3000 ppm) were assayed against the bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis sp*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella sp* using paper-disk method¹⁶.

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References

1. A. R. Katritzky and A. J. Boulton, *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1968, 9, 336.
2. S. H. Snyder, *Am. J. Psychiatry*, 1976, 133, 197.
3. B. Keshavan and J. Seetharamappa, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, 27, 815.
4. B. Keshavan and J. Seetharamappa, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1988, 18, 449.
5. B. Keshavan and Ramalingaiah, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1997, 9, 283.
6. P. W. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience, New York, 1960.
7. J. H. Van Vleck and N. Frank, *Phys. Rev.*, 1929, 34, 1494.
8. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1964.
9. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1986.
10. S. K. Agarwal and J. P. Tandon, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1979, 110, 401.
11. S. P. Sinha, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, 22, 57.
12. D. G. Karraker, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 1863.
13. J. Mohan, J. P. Tandon and N. S. Gupta, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, 111, 187.
14. F. J. Welcher, "The Analytical Use of EDTA", Van Nostrand, New York, 1965, Vol. 4.
15. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., ELBS, London, 1975.
16. F. C. Fahy and G. J. Presley, "Plant Bacterial Diseases : A Diagnostic Guide", Academic, New York, 1983.